

Social Vices: Causes and Counselling Remedies

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Abstract: Global increase in social problems both reflect and contribute to national and international tensions. The social vices problem is a key concern in many developing countries, where many types of vices are not known. It has worsened into a current global issue which represents human undesirable side of social growth. This undesirable fact is an unfortunate and has developed many security encounters facing the modern society. In this paper, some contemporary social vices have been discussed in the light of their causes, consequences, and possible counselling remedies. This paper argues that examination malpractice, drug abuse, child abuse, domestic violence and political thuggery among other contemporary social vices have created havoc and have contributed greatly to the slow pace in Nigeria. The major causes which include unemployment, poverty, peer influence, students' poor reading habit, quick success syndrome and lack of marital counselling with their effects were discussed. It has been established in the course of this study that the problem of social vices, is a symptom of society which is embroiled in moral decadence. Realizing the havoc which social vices have wrecked on individuals and the society at large, all hands must be on deck to combat the menace. However, to curb this menace, possible counselling remedies like Rational Emotive Therapy, Client-Centred therapy, Gestalt Therapy, Group Therapy, and family therapy were proffered to serve as a panacea which will stem the tide of social vices and foster rapid development. It was recommended that government and stakeholders should collaborate and ensure pre-marital counselling, marital counselling, drug abuse counselling, crisis counselling, sex counselling, counselling with families concerning children, vocational/career counselling, educational counselling as well as counselling delinquents are emphasized and recommended to curb the menace so as to promote individual, social, political, moral, educational and economic development.

Keywords: Child Abuse, Counselling, Domestic Violence, Drug Abuse, Social vices.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid social diverse acculturation rising from globalization has been recognized as a significant feature accountable for rise in social vices in contemporary societies [1]. In a historical perspective, a social vice presents when there is substantial variance between the principles of a society and its actual accomplishments. People have to struggle with these vices because they disrupt societal rules and values.

The social vices which have disintegrated into a current global matter portrays human undesirable side of social development. This destructive expansion is unfortunate and has become security challenge facing man in modern society. As observed by Chukwuemeka and Agbara, human civilization and in fact the whole world is simply and directly a complex object [2]. People and groups have their difficulties, requirements, ambitions, values, expectations, goals, feelings, and views which could be psychological political, social, economic, or religious. So, people, professional institution, agencies, and corporate bodies are burdened with the accountability of offering solutions to the flood of social vices fronting our contemporary societies. Aijboye et al. perceived direction counsellors are trained people who assist people confronted with one challenge or other [3]. Guidance counsellors practice many methods to manage maladaptive behaviours that could establish danger to the passive co-existence to the culture. The process of confirming peace in the people may start with determining intrapersonal conflict. So, the involvement of guidance counsellors as answer to social vices deemed necessary.

2 SOCIAL VICES: AN OVERVIEW

Social vices are practices, behaviors or habits generally considered immoral, sinful, rude, taboo, criminal or degrading in the associated society. The etymology of the two words; 'social' an English word which means 'relating to the society' and 'vice' a Latin word which translates 'defect or failing'. Social vices are extremely bad immoral behaviors that constitute a nuisance to the society, [4]. According to Jointheir social vices are forms of immoral, criminal, and wicked behaviors in the people [5]. These are social glitches and have been thought of as social establishments that a large number of viewers feel are unsuitable and need treating. Social vices are those actions that disturb societal rules and values. Social vices are also defined as a negative behavior that are in contradiction to norms of a society. It is very uncommon to find an institution negated of social vices. This portrays that they are all rampant in education centres as well as other social centres. Social vices are very common predominantly among young people even though adult males and females do engage in it too. Most of these vices plague the society and mitigate development.

Examples include prostitution, indecent dressing, rape, drug abuse, hooliganism, lesbianism, sodomy, alcoholism, incest, pedophilia, rape, kidnapping, smoking, pre-marital sexual activities, examination malpractice, terrorism, political thuggery, gambling, pocket picking, robbery, electoral malpractices, child abuse, cultism, corruption, bribery, domestic violence, internet crimes among others. In this discourse, five contemporary social vices vis-a vis drug abuse, examination malpractice, domestic violence, child abuse and political thuggery will be briefly discussed and their negative impacts at the individual level and the society at large.

2.1 Drug Abuse

Drug abuse is also called substance abuse. This is the continued misuse of drugs. It is an illness that is considered by a destructive outline of consuming a substance that leads to noteworthy problems or suffering. National Institute on drug Abuse (2003) describe drug abuse as the habit of illegal drugs and misuse of legal drugs. These drugs are misused for the purpose of recreation, alleged necessity, or convenience. Drug addiction has negative consequence to people and to the society. Drug addiction is viewed as a personality disorder and may also have been seen as a world-wide widespread with evolutionary inherited, physiological, and environmental influence controlling and affecting human behaviour. Anti-social behaviours occur when an individual get influenced of a drug and long-term personality changes in individual. Globally, the use has reached all-time high to the point of addiction. In addition to psychological, physical, and social damage, addiction drugs may lead to criminal consequences. Substances mostly abused include Cocaine, alcohol, methaqualone, barbiturates, cannabis, and some substituted amphetamines.

2.2 Examination Malpractice

Examination malpractice is anything done by the stakeholders, such as examination invigilators, parents, students, and teachers that is likely to reduce the valuation or make examination ineffective. For Umaru, it is any form of deceitful action that purposes at a better consequence than the candidate's actual intelligence performance [6]. Hiko mentions that examination malpractice is an unlawful or intolerable behavior by someone who break the examination rules at the time knowledge is being tested [7]. Olujoba and Daramola in [8] also defined exam malpractice as any form of irregularity in behavior showed by candidate or anybody charged with the conduct of examination in exam hall during examination. Examination Malpractice is one of the greatest menace and social vice confronting not only the educational sector but the entire nation because of its multiplier effect to various sectors of the economy.

2.3 Domestic Violence

Domestic violence otherwise called domestic abuse is a form of abuse by a person against another in a domestic background, e.g., marriage or cohabitation. The irresistible load of domestic violence is borne by women with serious health and social implication. It can be called intimate partner violence when done by a partner and can take place in heterosexual connection against the other partner [9]. Rightly defines domestic violence as an abusive behavior in a relationship which takes a number of forms of physical, sexual, verbal, and emotional abuse which can range from indirect, forced to violent physical forms such as choking, beating, women genital disfigurement, acid throwing. To Roberts, domestic violence may also include violence against parents, children, or the elderly people [10]. Domestic violence is one of the serious contemporary social vices that knows no religious, racial, cultural, or economic boundaries and has literally taken a residence in Nigeria with endless stories of pain and sorrow following it.

2.4 Child Abuse

Child abuse is a failure on the part of parent or guardian which consequences may result to death. It is an emotional or physical damage or an act which represents an imminent hazard of any damage. Federal Child Abuse Prevention and treatment Act (2003), perceives child abuse as any form of exploitation that can inflict harm physically, emotionally, socially, and psychologically. Forms of child abuse include child battering, child trafficking, sexual molestation and rape, neglect, emotional abuse, and abandonment. Nigeria Violence against Children (2014) with support from National Population Commission (NPC) and United Nations International Children's Fund (UNICEF) has revealed that out 1 of 10 Nigerian children experience at least one form of violence before they are 18years old. Similarly, the latest public opinion poll conducted by Ngozi Okwonjo Iweala opinion Polls (NOIPolls) in partnership with Protection Hub Nigeria (CPHub) in 2017 has exposed occurrence of 92% Child abuse in Nigeria.

2.5 Political Thuggery

Political thuggery is one of the contemporary social ills as seen by several scholars as a systematized arm of Nigerian politics. Ortese defines political thuggery as prepared violence, blackmail, and pressure against a political rival to achieve a self-centered political goal [11]. He additionally that political thuggery is a tool of violence structured against political rival. The use of thuggery since independence has spread and recently and it is means political influence without any contemplation for popular opinion of masses. Samson and Saawuan (2013) observed political thuggery as an act of violence meant at forcing opponents into releasing their political will [12].

3 CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF SOCIAL VICES

Recently, there have been a lot of discussions aimed at pinpointing the causes of social vices in our modern society which if not addressed with dispatch will deteriorate the society. It was revealed by the writer that, among the causes are major, which are primary causes and then the secondary causes which occur as a result of the primary causes. Below are the causes of the aforementioned social vices in our modern-day society as opined by Ariyo (2017) and Ukwu (2016) [4][13].

3.1 Unemployment

This is a situation whereby a person of workable age, willing and able to do work in unable to secure a paid employment [14]. It is not surprising that unemployment is mentioned as a cause of social vice, considering the large population of youth roaming the streets because they are unemployed and jobless despite being academically and physically fit. Following popular adage “An idle mind is a devil’s workshop”, If individuals who could have been fully engaged and busy contributing to the development of a nation in various sectors, found themselves being idle they cannot but start to think of any means of survival even if it means resorting to crime.

Unemployed youths now engage in crimes such as robbery, fraud, kidnapping, violent associations, violent demonstrations for pecuniary gains from unscrupulous, politicians engage them to do dirty jobs which has drastically increased terrorism and other social vices in our society. Foreign investors do fall victims of robbery which may cause a serious diplomatic conflict among the trading countries. Unemployment and general welfare also have made some youths very bitter and angry while the society is usually the recipient of their transferred aggression, whereby public peace is being disturbed as there are cases of public violence in our motor parks, urchins in the streets and marketplaces. Depression also led them to substance abuse and use of narcotic drugs for false sensation and recreation. It is apparent that unemployment causes depression and aggression which will lead to drug abuse and other forms of social vices.

3.2 Student Poor Reading Habits and Persistent Strike Action by Lecturers

Lackadaisical attitudes of parents and students in the modern society has contributed immensely to laziness and ‘I don’t care’ attitude of students towards academic activities which lead to examination malpractice. The students pay no or less attention to academic activities, thus poor reading habits. As such they engage in examination malpractice to aim for better result better than the candidate’s actual intelligence and performance. Persistent unnecessary strike actions where lecturers under associations embark on definite and indefinite strike actions which results to underutilization of the academic calendar. With this, curriculum is under covered, students are being rushed on crash programs which lead to students’ poor concentration and preparation for exams. Examination malpractice is one of the greatest social vices today because the issue is rampant in all school levels. The most alarming part of it all is that individuals who are supposed to be vigorously involved in the fight against this evil act are instead helping it in one way or the other [7].

3.3 Peer influence or Peer Pressure

The problems of cultism, prostitution and drug abuse are mainly as a result of peer influence and pressure. Drug abuse is regarded as a personality disorder, and it can be seen as an epidemic in the society. According to the writer peer pressure and curiosity can influence the incidence of drug abuse and the growth to addiction in a person’s life. Pressure of peer is major reason of youth participation in social vices. Due to their weak nature and tender age of students, they can easily be influenced. Curious children also have fun and explore new things which make them smoke and drink [4]. Peers abusing drugs are often at the danger of revealing adolescents to drug abuse and delinquent behavior. Research has exposed that, however, addressing such behaviour in intervention can be challenging [14]. Factors that make adolescents defenseless to drug and substance abuse are very low self-esteem, low academic achievement, family history, and scarcity of basic knowledge about the effects and dangers of consuming substances and peer pressure. Experimenting with drug even once may lead to addiction. Drug abuse has both short-term and long-term negative effects. Drugs induce dullness and impairs both physical and mental functioning of body and mind leading to compromised quality of life (Falco in [15]). Abusing drugs weakens the immune system which will make an individual vulnerable to acquire infections.

3.4 Poverty

Poverty is also a reason of modern social vices affecting Nigeria and many other countries. It is a state of comprehensive lack of nominal income of livelihood. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) recently released the 2019 Poverty report of Nigeria which highlights that 40 percent of the total population, or nearly 83 million persons, live below the country’s poverty line of 137,430 naira yearly. This gives birth to occurrence of high participation of its people in illegal actions e.g., corruption, political thuggery, kidnapping, corruption, and all types of immoral behaviors. Poverty as an idea may not be new in the world’s history book but the consciousness of it, is relatively new as a result of the economic breakdown, civil conflict, ethnic catastrophe [16]. The poor income to fulfil the basic needs of life, for they do not have basic properties to produce any income [17].

3.5 Lack of Pre-marital Counselling and Marital Counselling

Lack of pre-marital counselling and marital counselling has cause couples to find themselves unprepared for problem that rise after marriage, so they fail to control new situation, so option to ferocious behavior as way of resolving clashes in the family which at the end leads to divorce and broken homes. This violence is damaging forms of communication in the family. Potential pair are not aided to anticipate problems of married couple. When this type of problem arises, they are occupied by astonishment and their responses to those problems contrast. It has been observed that a number of them respond violently to each other [18]. Domestic violence condenses the family as such are unable to fulfil some of its important roles in the society. (Lessing in [18]).

Wellbeing of society is associated with the welfare of the family, it is not astonishing that there is some concern that this social institution is failing in its duties, (Dallan & Mchaughin in [18]). Many attempts have been made by social workers and their professional associates to fight against this menace, but very little has been achieved because domestic violence is still increasing day by day. Domestic Violence has a negative impact which leads to broken homes, single parenthood as a result of divorce. The writer is of the opinion that domestic violence can best be combated by the use of pre-marital and marital counselling. It is through marital counselling that partners will be exposed to realities of marital needs and the role of pre-marital counselling cannot be undermined because it serves as a preventive measure of family dysfunction. The writer concluded that pre-marital counselling decreases the occurrence of domestic violence, since as a key anticipation, it helps to avoid marital complications.

4 COUNSELLING REMEDIES TO SOCIAL VICIES

Collins in [19] indicates that through guidance and counselling, individuals and/or group of individuals are assisted to be disciplined and become able to deal with challenges and realities they face in their social and physical environment, realize their potentials, as well as identify opportunities in a world where chances for further training, employment and advancement continue to dwindle.

Counselling remedies are therapies carried out by a counsellor in resolving crisis or concern. There are treatment packages used to alter negative behavior to positive behavior. There can be seen as approaches that guide a counsellor to bring about therapeutic change [20]. Similarly, there are those techniques a counsellor employs to help a client or group of clients to overcome challenges which may be personal, Inter-personal or persona social. The field of counselling and psychotherapy today is dominated by three major theoretical orientations. Psychoanalytic, cognitive behavioral and humanistic theories. A fourth force, a transpersonal is also beginning to make its presence felt, and despite its lack of historical development, it is attracting a significant followership. Most of all the various counselling therapies emanate from one or more of these perspectives, each perspective differs significantly in terms of its human nature, the process of human development, the nature of maladaptive behavior depending on client characteristics, the role of counsellor, the techniques used and ultimately the goals of counselling [21]. From the findings of this study, the following counselling therapies tend to serve as remedies for the five contemporary social vices discussed above.

4.1 Rational Emotive Therapy (RET)

RET therapy is based on the assumption that human beings are both with a portion of rational and irrational thinking. This therapy was developed by Albert Ellis (1913-2007) [22]-[25]. The goal of this therapy is for a client to control emotional conflicts, reduction of self-defeating behaviours. In rational emotive therapy, attempts are made to rearrange an individual's belief system into more logical views [19]. According to the therapy, rationality denotes to persons using effective, and scientific ways of endeavouring to attain their values [26]. Ellis, in his various publications says that many people lead unhappy and sometimes even psychologically disordered lives because they harbor such irrational, unrealistic ideas. Such ideas he stated include the following:

- a. That it is necessary to have the love and endorsement of every significant individual for everything we do.
- b. That should be thoroughly competent, adequate, and successful in all possible respects if we are to consider ourselves worthwhile.
- c. That It is terrible when things don't turn out the way we want them to be.

Egbule says that in order to lead clients to eliminate such maladaptive cognitions and adapt more effective thinking, rational emotive counsellors take a directive role during therapy; openly challenging outlines of thought that seem to be dysfunctional [26]. The therapist may say: "why do you think that for the fact that you are not employed this year means you will never get employed again?" "Why do you think that because you didn't get good grades this year you won't get good grades next year?" "Why do you think that for the fact your marriage is a living hell now you will never have a peaceful marriage?" and so on. By nature, human beings have the propensities of self-destruction, procrastination, and endless replication of mistakes, intolerance, superstition, and escaping of realizing growing potentials. Rational Emotive therapy efforts to help clients admit themselves as creatures who will endure to make errors, yet at the same time understand to live more at peace within themselves. By pointing out the clients' logic, the therapist employing this form of treatment believes they can help people adopt a more review of themselves and their circumstances [19].

4.2 Gestalt Therapy

This is an approach that has a holistic view of the clients' thoughts, behavior and feelings. This therapy views an individual's perceptions, body and thoughts, are in agreement with each other; where consciousness leads to development, accountability and maturity. Egbule says that Gestalt therapy inspires the client to become conscious of their feelings and take charge of their own actions [19].

This therapy tries to increase the client's emotional expressiveness, bring unconscious feelings into conscious awareness and the clients to change maladaptive ways of thinking and behaving. It insists that clients take responsibility for their actions instead of blaming other people or events for their problems. Those clients should see things as there are now rather than in their distant past, in the future or in some other places or times. It is of the view that people who are aware of their feeling can control the feelings and their reactions to events. This type of therapy can be employed by the counsellor for the treatment of drug abuse, alcoholism, and political thuggery which do all have negative impact on the client and the larger society which results from personality and career mismatch, poor reading habits, irrational emulation due to excessive interest for quick success syndrome etc. so also it can serve as a good therapy to assist drug abusers.

4.3 Group Therapy

The group therapy became popular during Second World War when therapies discovered that the clients, they needed to attend to were more than they could cope with. They devised a means by putting them into groups. This was the beginning of group therapy. Here, this therapy will help curb the menace of examination malpractice where the therapist can attend to more clients within a short period of time, and at a limited cost. The clients have come across role models, shared their experience with other clients', have feedback about their behavior, and assurance that they are not alone in their problems. These do provide some emotional relief as in the case of child abuse clients. So also, this therapy can be helpful in counselling political thugs. It allows people with unrelated issues and background to come together and share experiences. A group is made of six to fourteen clients. Here, issues like alcoholism and drug addiction may be taken into consideration. People who may or may not be alcoholic or addicts will share in the discussion each providing their type of therapeutic model to be used which will depend on the therapist and the goals to be set will be done by the whole group. Egbule has reported two different types of group therapy, these two types of group therapies have been found to be effective [19].

- i. Psychodrama: Here, drama is organized with characters showing traits of the problems under treatment while clients watch, insights to behavioral changes are provided and clients learn from such insights.
- ii. Transactional Analysis: This is a type of group therapy that helps clients change their immature or inappropriate ways of relating to other people, relating, or reacting to situations. It involves the display of roles of Id, Ego, and Super Ego

4.4 Client- Centred Therapy

This is the most commonly practiced of all humanistic therapies. Today it is mostly called Person- Centred Therapy. It was developed by Carl Rogers (1902-1981). The goal of the therapy is for a client to become more self-directed, increase positive self-regard; and choose his goals. Egbule says that Carl Rogers has been the most influential of all contemporary psychotherapists [19]. This type of therapy is a non-directive counselling therapy as it helps clients to find their own answers to their problems, thereby go towards the way of self-actualization. This mode of therapy gives no advice but helps to enhance client's ability for self-actualization. It is believed that a problem arises because of the conflict between a person's public life and image of his actual self, causing incongruence. It is the duty of the therapist or counsellor to make the client think more realistically about himself, his ability, and his goal. The client is helped towards making unconditional positive regard of himself. Carl Rogers says that the person – centered therapy is a therapy in which the goal is to reach one's potential for self-actualization.

4.5 Family Therapy

This is a type of therapy where one, two or more members of the family are involved. A concern can be treated may be with one, two or more of the family members The individual considered as the motivator of family therapy and work with relatives as a unit is Nathan Ackerman, a child psychiatrist and trained in psychoanalysis. The logic of this therapy is that sometimes problems with a members of the family may affect relationship with other members of the family.

In his therapeutic line, Ackerman was direct, honest, and open by inspiring families to share their own feelings as he did. He became emotionally engaged with the family while at the same time observing for unconscious themes in his work [27]. There are number of family therapists were tired of his engaging and his active method to therapy. Egbule says that in most families, members play rigid roles, and this contributes to conflict [19]. One member may always have the last say with oilier roles permanently, a scapegoat, bully and so on. A family therapy is a type of therapy that encourages the constructive expression of feelings and the establishments of rules that family members agree to follow [19]. The duty of therapist is to assess the duty of each member and to see there are some structural malformation, or one person is overplaying his role bringing about problems in that family or that such a problem of malformation or over action of a member that is adversely affecting the other or others. Family therapy enhances the inter-member relationship of the family and their wellbeing. According to the writer, this therapy will be appropriate for the treatment of domestic violence, and it forms by a counsellor.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Social vices are seen as bad personalities, negative and unhealthy behaviors that are against morality of a society. The problem of social vices is a symptom of society which is embroiled in moral decadence. Some contemporary social vices have been discussed with regards to their reasons, consequences, and probable counselling remedies. Examination malpractice, drug abuse, child abuse, domestic violence and political thuggery among other contemporary social vices were discussed in the paper which have created havoc and have contributed greatly to the slow pace in Nigeria.

The major causes which include unemployment, poverty, peer influence, students' poor reading habit, quick success syndrome and lack of marital counselling and their effects were also discussed. Realizing the havoc which social vices have wrecked on individuals and the society at large. It has been established in the course of this study, the possible counselling remedies like Rational emotive therapy, Client-centred therapy, Gestalt therapy, Group therapy and Family therapy were proffered to serve as a panacea which will stem the tide of social vices and foster rapid development. It is noteworthy that, research has shown that there are little differences in the effectiveness of the types of therapeutic styles. Although the rate of improvement of clients may vary, there are usually appreciative improvements that are noticed. A therapist can adopt a technique suitable for any particular concern or a combination of techniques as the therapist may deem it wise, that is to say, different types of therapies can be combined to solve a particular problem. For effectiveness of a particular type of therapeutic approach, the characteristics of the therapist, the therapy and the client need to be considered.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and discussions from this paper, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. Vocational career counselling services should be emphasized as an integral part of educational goals which in return will reduce the tension of unemployment and poverty in order for graduates to be self-reliant and also involve in vocational trades to promote educational, career, personal, personal-social and economic development.
2. There is need for marital, pre-marital, and post-marital counselling among people to help address issues of pre-marital sexual activities, domestic violence, grapple of coping and adjusting with sexual maturity and the like, in order to produce beneficial changes in disturbed matrimony or families.
3. Drug counselling is a preventive measure as such should be given special attention. Drug education should be directed towards behavioral change since drug abuse is a behaviour.
4. Broad based programme of pre-marital counselling coupled with adequate sex education is crucial and should be inculcated in couples, adolescent, and youths in developing countries like Nigeria where many parents, teachers, Pastors, and others feel that adolescents should not be exposed to sex education.
5. Professional educational guidance and counselling should direct attention to effective realization of the educational aims and objectives as put forward in Nigerian National policy on Education.

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